

Development of Structural Graphite/Epoxy Tube for Space Application

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ABSTRACT

For the purpose of lightening future spacecraft structures, trial manufacturing tests of the tube truss structure made from graphite/epoxy, which is superior in respect of specific strength-modulus and dimensional stability, were performed.

This paper presents the establishment of manufacturing and processing methods for graphite/epoxy tubes with lightweight joints, strength tests of the trial manufacturing components, and the trial assembly of the structure from those components.

As the result of the trial manufacturing tests, a 30 - 40% weight reduction was attained in the graphite/epoxy tube truss structure compared to one made from aluminium.

Also, identified was the use of multi-stepped lap joints which lowered the shear stress concentration at the joints by 30% as compared to single-stepped lap joints.

INTRODUCTION

Development of graphite/epoxy composites for space structures has been progressing and now will be applied to the spacecraft module support system. This study was performed to develop basic material and process data for graphite/epoxy tube truss structures through the following experimental activities.

- (1) Selection of the materials and the fabrication processes for the joints of graphite/epoxy tube truss components.
- (2) Verification of the actual joint strength.
- (3) Fabrication and assembly of the tube truss structure.

The results of this study will be applied to the structural design of the module support system developed as a general purpose subsystem for large scale satellites.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

The properties of the materials selected for the graphite/epoxy tube and the joints are summarized in table 1 and 2.

Table 1 Materials and Properties

	Spec.	Modulus of Elasticity	Inter Laminar Shear Strength	Shear Modulus	Coefficient of Thermal Expansion
Ti-6A -4V Sheet	MIL-T-9046 Type3 Comp.C	11250kgf/mm ²	-	-	9x10 ⁻⁶ /°C
Graphite/epoxy Prepreg Tape	M1540	11700kgf/mm ²	10.9kgf/mm ²	-	-0.5x10 ⁻⁶ /°C
Graphite/epoxy Prepreg Cloth	M1543	6000kgf/mm ²	5kgf/mm ²	-	0.5x10 ⁻⁶ /°C
Epoxy Film Adhesive	M1115 Type I	40kgf/mm ²	-	278kg/mm ²	7.5x10 ⁻⁶ /°C

Table 2 Outgassing Data of Graphite/epoxy

Material	Test Method	TML	CVCM
M1540	ASTM E-595 125°Cx24h (5x10 ⁻⁵ Torr)	0.56%	0.02%
M1543		0.56%	0.02%

Fabrication

The sequence of fabrication processes is as shown Fig. 1. Sheet rolling followed by tape winding was used to lay-up graphite/epoxy prepreg materials for tube components.¹⁾

Fig. 1 Fabrication Sequence of Graphite/Epoxy Tube

Adhesive Bonding Test

Graphite/epoxy to Ti alloy adhesive bonding tests were carried out to optimize the bonding process. The configuration of the double lap shear test specimen is given in Fig. 2. The test results are given in Fig. 3 and 4. The results show the cocure process using staged adhesive films gave the highest shear strength.

Fig.2 Configuration of Test Specimen

Fig. 3 Staging Effect of Cocured Joint

Fig. 4 Comparison of Various Bonding Process

Joint Strength Test

Graphite/epoxy tube to Ti adapter joint tests were performed to determine the actual strength. The configuration of the test tubes and the test results are given in Fig. 5 and table 3 respectively. Photographs of the fracture are shown in Figs. 6 and 7. The results show the joint strength meet the design requirement. Also it was confirmed that the multisteped lap joint makes the shear stress concentration at the joint 30% lower than the single-stepped joint²⁾, therefore the multi-stepped joints were selected as the lightweight joining method of the graphite/epoxy tube truss components.

Fig. 5 Configuration of Test Tube

Table 3 Test Results

	Load(max.kg)	Fracture
Compression	21500	Graphite/epoxy Compression Failure at Joint
Tension	18333	Graphite/epoxy Tension Failure at Joint

Fig. 6 Fracture after Compression Test

Fig. 7 Fracture after Tension Test

Fabrication and Assembling the Tube Truss Structure

The specifications of the assembled tube truss structure for the spacecraft module support system are summarized in Fig. 8. The resultant structure showed the following advantages.

- . 30 - 40% weight savings as compared to conventional Al alloy structure.
- . Good installability to mission modules and launch rocket structure.

Fig. 9 shows the assembled structure on which dummy plastics covers are installed.

Fig. 8 Basic Specification of Tube Truss Structure

Fig. 9 Assembled Graphite/epoxy Tube Truss Structure

FUTURE STUDIES

The above test results proved the feasibility of our basic concepts for graphite/epoxy tube structure for space applications. The following studies are being planned for the future.

- 1 Weight savings by substitution of graphite/epoxy for the metal fittings and use of Kevlar/epoxy for the box covers.
- 2 Weight savings by substitution of metal matrix composites for the plate and honeycomb core.
- 3 Graphite/epoxy use on antenna structure, its supports and solar array panels.
- 4 Applications composite materials to future satellites and large space structures.

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